

ADVANTAGES OF EARLY ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT USING NON-REMOVABLE EQUIPMENT.

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Introduction.

The decision on the expediency of early orthodontic treatment is still being questioned. This is due to the poor hygienic status, the difficulty of cooperation with patients and the ineffectiveness of treatment, since subsequently the need to use non-removable equipment remains relevant.

Purpose of the research.

Study the effectiveness of the use of orthodontic equipment during the period of replacement bite.

Materials and methods.

35 patients aged 6-13 years with dental anomalies were examined in accordance with the requirements of the Ministry of Health. 15 removable devices were used, 15 non-removable, and in 5 cases a partial bracket system was used.

Results of research.

Of the 35 patients, 9 people were treated initially using non-removable equipment, and then teething control was carried out using removable orthodontic equipment (1st grade). In 14 people, treatment was carried out only using removable equipment (2nd grade). 8 people continued orthodontic treatment using non-removable equipment during the period of permanent bite (3rd grade). In 4 patients, orthodontic treatment was consistent using removable and non-removable techniques, but did not lead to correction of the occlusion anomaly, only a decrease in the degree of malocclusion was observed. (4th gr.) Complications in the form of a violation of the enamel structure during the use of orthodontic equipment were observed in 3 people from group 1, which was associated with poor oral hygiene and the areas of enamel damage did not depend on the elements of orthodontic equipment. Among the patients of the 2nd group, enamel demineralization was observed in 2 people, 1 patient had resorption of the root of a permanent tooth as a complication at the stage of eruption of permanent teeth. Among the patients of the 3rd group, characteristic chalky spots were found around the elements of non-removable equipment in 8

people. Among the patients of the 4th group of the study, 3 people had pronounced forms of gingivitis and enamel demineralization.

Conclusions.

1. Shortening the time of orthodontic treatment using non-removable equipment is an advantage when choosing orthodontic devices.
2. The use of non-removable equipment in the early period of bite formation prevents or minimizes the formation of anomalies in the position of individual teeth and reduces the overall duration of orthodontic treatment.

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